

Impacts of Social Worker and Social Change on Mental Health

Rajanna G.

Faculty, Department of Social Work, Bangaluru North University,
Kolar.

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ABSTRACT:

This article discusses the effects of social change on mental health and social worker role. It seems likely that no society can be utterly stable, despite reports of primitive societies or peasant communities which convey the impression of an unchanged and unchanging cultural history. The most critical and widespread source of social change in the contemporary world lies in the complex of technological and industrial advances. The consequences of the Industrial Revolution can be traced further in its implications for education, social legislation and childbearing practices. Even more remote effects on public health practices, on disease and on mental health remain the subjects of continuing study.

KEYWORDS:

Social Work, Social Change, Socio-technology, Mental health, Counselling, Hospitals, Disorders.

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Introduction:

Social workers provide a wide spectrum of direct services to the public, from counseling students with behavioral problems to developing treatment plans for those struggling with substance abuse. This hands-on support has helped countless people from diverse cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds take charge of their health and well-being, leading to a higher quality of life.

While many equate social work careers with case management and clinical settings, the field offers a variety of employment options for those with the right qualifications. If you're interested in pursuing a career in social work and mental health, it's important to understand how these two disciplines are intertwined and which roles will allow you to make a real difference in your community.

Social Work and Mental Health:

From the beginning, social work and mental health have been inextricably linked. The social work field can trace its roots back to the turn of the 20th century, according to the National Association of Social Workers (NASW). This is when the first academic class in social work was offered at Columbia University. Less than a decade later, sweeping mental health reform in the U.S. drew greater attention to psychological disorders, leading to the creation of the National Committee for Mental Hygiene. This agency, later renamed Mental Health America (MHA), helped facilitate more than 100 child guidance clinics and advocated for mental illness awareness through research, public communication and policy making.

The Role of the Modern Days Mental Health Social Worker:

In the years since its inception, the social work field has been on the frontline of countless cultural, economic and health-related causes, including Social Security, unemployment benefits and disability pay. Alongside advocating for fair and equitable health care programs, many social work practitioners including mental health social workers, also assess, diagnose and treat mental illnesses, behavioral disorders and emotional issues. Some examples include:

Depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder and other mental health conditions
Child abuse, neglect and behavioral problems. Addiction, substance abuse and alcoholism
Significant life events, including divorce, bereavement and terminal illnesses
Coping with unemploy-

ment, homelessness and long-term disabilities .Mental health social workers support individuals, families and communities as they seek to overcome challenges that negatively impact individual and community well-being. For example, by addressing a patient's substance abuse issues, social workers can help recovering addicts find new employment, obtain affordable housing and take advantage of available mental health services.

Job Description of Mental Health Social Worker:

Mental health social workers engage mostly with clients struggling to overcome addictive behaviors, such as drug or alcohol abuse, or mental health conditions, such as eating disorders, clinical depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) among others. Although the exact daily duties of mental health social workers can vary based on their employer and the patient population they focus on, common responsibilities may include the following:

- Establishing rapport and building relationships with clients
- Assessing clients' mental health needs
- Researching mental health resources for clients, such as substance abuse rehabilitation programs and suicide prevention resources
- Providing clients with information about resources based on their specific needs
- Varying Roles of Social Work in Mental Health
- Social workers' roles in mental health include mental health research, treatment and prevention. Demand for social workers who specialize in mental health and substance abuse is only growing — employment in these roles is expected to increase 12% between 2020 and 2030, according to the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS).

Clinical Social Workers:

Clinical social workers use their knowledge, skills and experience to help patients with mental illnesses assess, diagnose and treat their conditions. Unlike standard practices in psychology, clinical social work takes into account the environmental and societal factors that impact a client's physical, mental and emotional well-being. Clinical social workers address a wide range of mental health challenges, from substance abuse and addiction to childhood trauma and behavioral disorders. This scope allows them to work in a variety of practice settings and assist patients who have very different needs.

School Social Workers:

School social work is a specialized practice area that focuses on the development and mental health of students in the U.S. education system. These social workers are considered trained mental health professionals and provide hands-on assistance to children and young adults who present with mental illnesses, persistent behavioral problems and learning disabilities. Working alongside teachers, faculty and parents, school social workers offer positive behavioral and academic support to help students meet their full potential, according to the School Social Work Association of America.

Substance Abuse Social Workers:

Substance abuses social workers specialize in diagnosing and treating cases of addiction and dependency. They work with patients to reduce drug and alcohol consumption, identify the root causes of addiction and create detailed treatment plans. Substance abuse social workers are often employed at hospitals, detoxification centers and other mental health clinics where recovering addicts may be staying, according to the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Ser-

vices Administration.

Where Do Mental Health Social Workers Work?

Here are a few examples of where mental health social workers are employed and how each setting is unique:

Hospitals: Mental health social workers provide front line services to patients in hospitals and medical facilities after an accident has occurred. However, the type of work they perform depends on their role– clinical social workers might be responsible for conducting psychological assessments, while non-clinical staff could focus on determining which mental health services a patient is eligible for, according to the NASW. Other key tasks include crisis management, direct counseling or therapy, case management and treatment plan development.

Mental health clinics: Clinical social workers employed in mental health settings, such as inpatient or outpatient facilities, provide essential case management and direct client services, including group therapy and crisis intervention. They work with patients struggling with substance abuse, eating disorders, mental illnesses and the stress of everyday life. Beyond treating mental health conditions, these social workers also educate clients about self-care and help them build the social, financial and interpersonal skills to lead comfortable and fulfilling lives.

Private practices: Some clinical social workers choose to open their own private practices. While this career path does come with strict licensing requirements, it offers practitioners a way to set their own schedules and choose the types of clients they want to support. Social work private practices typically offer individual and group therapy, substance abuse counseling and other mental health services provided by standard mental health professionals. They can also be contracted by companies to improve employee assistance

programs and expand an organization's mental health resources.

Social change in India:

India as a fast-developing country in at the threshold of technological and industrial change of a significant proportion. Knowledge change is invariably, accompanied by psychological and social unrest. And rise in psychiatric morbidity. The changes are difficult pursue at psychological levels by lay people, Bus has changes accelerate. The problems created by the changes force themselves. And perceived even by ordinary man is alarming. This is more significant in the rural district and areas undergoing rapid industrialization. These rapid changes in society and technology have caused change in the human population and environment inevitably creating health hazards and seriously imparting the quality of life.

The term Socio technological change Reflex the non-widely recognized fact that there is a casual relationship between technological change and social change. For example, to the introduction of mass production technology work becomes fragmented, changing from the completion of well-defined job activity with distinct and recognized end products to one of numerous and highly specified subjects with little apparent relationship to the end product, the growing size of factory units have tended to result in longevity of the command.

The effect on mental health of social and technological changes are both positive and negative intrinsically, new technologies are neither good nor bad. Their consequences are almost entirely a function of bondman does with them in social context in which they are introduced. Positive effects of new technologies may have a good effect on mental health. For example, improve agricultural techniques, alternative energy sources, environmental hygiene and mass education, negative. Even a catastrophic effect

may be seen in the form of fear of nuclear holocaust, environmental pollution and drug abuse.

The Concept of Mental Health:

Before the impact of change on mental health can be discussed, it must be made clear what is meant by mental health. Mental health covers an elusive and diffuse field and the term itself encompasses a multiplicity of meanings. It can be considered as a medical, psychological or a social phenomenon. The medical view of mental health is dominated by bio physiological phenomena. The most rudimentary medical health is that an individual's psychic functions are at a level deemed satisfactory.

Some of the factors of social and technological change leading to conflict between biological man and his new man-made cultural environment, and the mental health hazards they have created, can be broadly viewed as follows.

Urbanization:

The social environment is inextricably linked with the bio-physical one. The rapid urban growth in India has led to improvised housing, bad sanitation, and inadequate provision of services of all kinds.

Socioeconomic factors:

The economic environment in which man lives Grows up and works. Also, effects are susceptibility to illnesses and chance of his responding to an insufficient milieu By Pursuing divine patterns of behaviors. Income and occupation standards of housing sanitation and nutrition.

Population Pressure:

The meteoric increase in population in India, mainly due to

better medical facilities, has led to 2 specific problems. One is the crucial medical and psychological effects of cooperation growth, and the other is overcrowding.

Geographic and Social mobility:

Movement of people with India is increasing at a brisk pace during the Last few decades. People are at times forced to move by calamities for social pressure factors out of their control. They may migrate as a result of poor job opportunities in their old habitat to seek better pay or improved standard of living.

Changing family Patterns:

With the rapid socio technological change that Indian society is undergoing one of the first codicil institutions to be affected is family. The structure of the family is Altering. It is seen that more and more extended families are becoming nuclear. The dissolution of the extended family has deprived family members of traditional support they give to each other, to the elderly to the sick and disabled.

The influence of the mass media on mental health:

Mass media is powerful tool which can and is being used in India for the promotion of varied ideas and expectations and awareness of people. Visual communication television, for instance, is used to inform and educate the public both overtly and covertly on matters for pertaining to health and happiness.

Alcohol and Drug Abuse:

In the past, research in this field has stressed individual Psychopathology is to identify and evaluate the social factors leading to drinking behavior. It is well-known that certain communities sanction the use of alcohol. While in others drinking is frowned upon in one study, but author it was found that alcohol consumption was

significantly more among the Catholics of Goa, then the Hindus are much less among the Muslims of that area.

Crime, and its effects on health and behavior:

There is need for more studies on crime and its social consequences. Crime is mall adaptive patron of behavior generated largely due to social stresses. Mentally healthy community would naturally have a low crime rate. But the incidence of crime is on the increase. And in one it's nature and motivations are changing towards senseless political motivation.

Violence and aggression:

Occasion behavior is a part of the basic human nature. It is an adaptable behavior among its own horizons and genetically coordinate new mechanisms, that are created upon both hormonal and psychological Factors. It has multiple determinants and varies with sex, age and culture. It promotes the survival of the species and cultural group. Violence is aggression misdirected. It is a short term coping mechanism that promotes adjustment in short term, But that proves mall adaptive in the long run to the individual and society.

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